

THE BENEFITS OF LEARNING MULTIPLE LANGUAGES SIMULTANEOUSLY.

Gulnora Abdullaeva Gaybulloevna

teacher of English Linguistics department,
Bukhara State University
g.g.abdullaeva@buxdu.uz.

Bafayeva Zarnigor Bakhodirovna

student of Foreign Languages Faculty,
Bukhara State University
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Abstract.

This article discusses the benefits of learning several languages, being bilingual, at the same time. Bilingualism has been found to enhance cognitive development, improve language skills, increase cultural awareness, provide access to increased job opportunities, and enhance executive functioning in children. Research studies have shown that bilingual children outperform monolingual children in various language and cognitive tasks. By promoting bilingualism in early childhood education, children can develop the skills they need to succeed in a diverse and globalized world, and society can become more inclusive and understanding. Therefore, it is essential for educators and parents to encourage bilingualism in children through various means such as exposing them to a second language at home, enrolling them in bilingual education programs, or providing opportunities to interact with speakers of other languages

Key words: bilingualism, multilingualism, cognitive development, language, advantages, children, education.

Introduction

People need a way of communication organized in a specific environment. This process is often called language. Although the term language may seem difficult to define precisely due to its social complexity, linguists generally agree that language is a system of signs designed for communication purposes. System is the whole of things organized and arranged to work together to perform a specific task. Language, as a form of communication between people, has many features such as being governed by rules, it is a system and performs tasks. It has functions such as providing information, expressing feelings and emotions, achieving consensus, exercising authority, and identification. Because people use more than one language, words such as bilingual, bilingual, and multilingual were born. The word polyglot is at the center of this article and is derived from two Latin words; 'veel' meaning 'many' and 'lingua' meaning 'language'.

Therefore, multilingualism is defined as the ability of a speaker to speak several languages equally and independently with knowledge of the native language. However, it was found that monolingualism tended to predominate in most language groups compared to other groups in both written and oral performances. Multilingualism can also be considered as the presence of more than one language in a society. These many languages can be formal or informal, domestic or foreign, national or international. Sometimes many languages are used in the same way as speaking two languages. This skill refers to the ability to speak two languages simultaneously. In this context, multilingualism is considered to be bilingual (the ability to speak two languages fluently), trilingual (the ability to speak three languages), and in some cases even the same speaker is considered to have the ability to speak more than three languages. Since the prefix 'multi' refers to more than one language, technically both bilingual and trilingual will be used in more than one language. As we use more languages, we become multilingual.

Literature review

Many studies have already been conducted to explain the positive effects of being able to speak more than one language at the same time. According to Grosjean F., bilingualism, or the ability to speak and understand two languages, has become very important in today's world. According to the United Nations, more than 7,000 languages are spoken worldwide, and bilingualism is the majority in many countries. Research shows that half of the world's population is bilingual or multilingual. (Grosjean F., 2010, p. 174) In general, children their age have the ability and ability to learn more than one language. There are many lovers of the language. This concept is closely related to how children perceive language and how their language develops. In fact, there are many factors that affect them such as age, language, relationships. Raising bilingual children is not just a problem, it is a challenge. There are a number of myths about bilingualism, especially about teaching children a second language early, such as language delay, personality differences, brain confusion, or language mixing contributing to confusion. In the past, bilingualism was considered a factor in language development. Many parents fear that their children will experience language delays if they learn two different languages at the same time. But the truth is that speech and language delays can have many causes, often neurological or physiological. However, there is no conclusive evidence that bilingualism exists. Moreover, one myth about being bilingual is that two languages mean two or different cultures. It is clear that bilinguals, like bilinguals, match their behavior

across different situations and people. This often leads to bilingualism. This phenomenon shows that language is a special system. As Grosjean says, after restructuring, bilingual languages often reach the level of languages necessary for new human life (Grosjean F., 2010, p. 244). One of the main concerns parents experience when raising bilingual children is confusion. When bilingual children mix words from two languages in a sentence, it is often perceived as a sign of confusion. We call this code mixing. In fact, code mixing is a natural and normal part of bilingual development, and bilingual children are indeed well motivated to code mix, Barac and Bialystok, (2012). Rather than being a sign of confusion, code mixing can be viewed as an indicator of bilingual children's language creativity (Heinlein and Williams, 2013).

Methods

This article is based on a survey conducted among 4th year students of the BSU Department of Foreign Languages. The education mentioned in this article is not only formal but also formal education. Students were asked questions about the benefits of bilingualism. While more than 70% of the participants expressed their views on the benefits of bilingualism, others stated that they were strongly against being bilingual. The subject is qualitative research. The benefits of speaking more than one language have been identified based on written analysis of educational and psychology literature.

Discussion

This section aims to discuss the benefits of bilingualism. One of the main benefits of learning a language relates to cognitive development. Cognitive development refers to the process of children acquiring and developing their thinking, problem-solving and learning skills. Bilingualism has been shown to have a positive impact on children's cognitive development. Research has shown that bilingual children develop a flexible intelligence that allows them to easily switch between tasks and ideas (Bialystok, 2011). Bilingual children also tend to have better working memory, allowing them to remember and process information more efficiently (Carlson and Meltzoff, 2008). Moreover, bilingualism has been associated with increased attention and inhibitory control, skills that are crucial for academic success (Bialystok & Martin, 2004). This study shows that bilingualism in early childhood education may benefit children's cognitive development.

Moreover, Research studies have shown that bilingual children have better language proficiency in both of their languages compared to monolingual children (Bialystok, 2001). Bilingual children have also been found to have a

larger vocabulary and better grammar than monolingual children (Barac & Bialystok, 2012). Furthermore, exposure to two languages from an early age has been linked to better reading and writing skills in children (Lesaux, Rupp, & Siegel, 2007). These findings suggest that bilingualism in early childhood education can have significant benefits for language development in children, which can improve their academic success and communication skills in the future.

Bilingualism has also been found to increase cultural awareness in children. When children learn a second language, they are also exposed to different cultures, traditions, and ways of life. This exposure can broaden their perspectives and help them appreciate and understand different cultures.

In addition to the cognitive and linguistic benefits, bilingualism can also increase job opportunities for individuals in the future. In today's global economy, companies and organizations often seek employees who are fluent in more than one language to help them connect with diverse customers, clients, and partners. Research studies have shown that bilingualism can increase earning potential and career opportunities. For example, a study by Chiswick and Miller (2010) found that bilingualism can lead to higher wages, especially for individuals who speak high-demand languages such as Spanish, French, and Chinese.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, bilingualism in early childhood education has been found to have numerous benefits for children, including enhanced cognitive development, improved language skills, increased cultural awareness, increased job opportunities, and enhanced executive functioning. Bilingual children outperform monolingual children in various language and cognitive tasks. Given these benefits, educators and parents need to encourage bilingualism in children, whether by exposing them to a second language at home, enrolling them in bilingual education programs, or providing them with opportunities to interact with speakers of other languages. By promoting bilingualism in early childhood education, we can help children develop the skills they need to succeed in a diverse and globalized world, and we can create a more inclusive and understanding society.

Reference:

1. A. M. Mazrui. Swahili State and Society: The Political Economy of an African Language, East African Education Publishers, Nairobi, 1995.
2. Abdullayeva, G. (2022). LEARNERS' PSYCHOLOGY AS ONE OF THE MAIN ISSUES INFLUENCING LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 11(11). <http://journal.buxdu.uz>.

3. buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/download/6321/4013
4. Abdullayeva, G. G. (2023). LANGUAGE LEARNING AND PSYCHOLOGY. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(2), 555-560.
<http://farspublishers.org/index.php/ijessh/article/view/520>
5. Abdullayeva, G. G. . (2023). Ways of Motivating Young Learners in EFL Classroom. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 122-124.
<http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1109>
6. Barac & Bialystok, (2012). Bilingual Effects on Cognitive and Linguistic Development: Role of Language, Cultural Background, and Education.
7. Ellen Bialystock, (2017). The Bilingual Adaptation: How Minds Accommodate Experience
8. Gaybulloyevna, G. A. (2022, January). Factors affecting language learning process. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 277-279).
9. Grosjean, F. (2010). Bilingual: Life and reality. Harvard University Press.
10. H. Bussmann. Rout ledge Dictionary of Language and linguistics, Rout ledge, London, 1996.
11. Heinlein and Williams (2013). Bilingualism in the Early Years: What the Science Says.
12. J. Mutiga. The Impact of a National Language on other Indigenous Languages: The Case of Kenya. In Proceedings of 17th-18th March on Across Borders: Benefiting from cultural differences, DAAD Regional Office in Africa, Nairobi, 2005.
13. J.Lyons. Language and Linguistics: An Introduction, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1981.
14. Lesaux, Rupp, & Siegel, (2007). Growth in Reading Skills of Children From Diverse Linguistic Backgrounds: Findings From a 5-Year Longitudinal Study.
15. M. Mwololo. Are You Fluent in Your Mother Language? In Daily Nation, Living, February 20th, Nation Media Group, Nairobi, 3, 2008.
16. N. O. Ogechi, Kembo-Sure. Linguistic Human Rights in Kenya. In Proceedings of 17th-18th March on Across Borders: Benefiting from cultural differences, DAAD Regional Office in Africa, Nairobi, 25-42, 2005.
17. Stephanie M. Carlson & Meltzoff (2008). Bilingual experience and executive functioning in young children.
18. V. Fromkin, R. Rodman, N. Hyams, eds. An Introduction to Language, Thomson Wordsworth, USA, 2007